

Change of Technology in the Shrimp Sector in Ecuador: From diesel engines to electric engines for water pumping

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Ecuador is currently the first shrimp exporter in the world. The shrimp farming area is approximately 250,000 Ha. In 2020, production reached 1142Kg of shrimp per Ha.

The pre-feasibility project that is being planned energetically has to do with the change in technology from diesel engines to electric engines for pumping water, in order to be more efficient in the use of energy and be more environmentally sustainable.

The policy of technological substitution and/or energy sources may influence GDP in an unexpected way and may have unanticipated side effects that negatively affect production in other sectors of the economy, which could lead to a decrease in production at the national level.

INTRODUCTION

Shrimp production has been increasing due to the proliferation of shrimp farms on the Ecuadorian coast, to the point of positioning Ecuador among the top world exporters, in addition to contributing to the growth of the world supply of this product. The drop in international prices in the current scenario shows a reality that must be addressed.

On the other hand, the government has stated that, due to the current economic crisis, it will be necessary to remove fuel subsidies, including diesel. In this context, since diesel is used for pumping systems, it allows the situation in the shrimp sector to have higher production costs.

According to the Global Aquaculture Advocate, diesel has a participation of between 7 to 15% in production costs, depending on the efficiency of the pumping systems and the productivity levels of the shrimp farms of their specific production model.

In this scenario, the shrimp sector faces many challenges, such as being more efficient and competitive, and how to optimize resources and reduce production costs. In this case, energy efficiency plays a very important role in the optimization of technology and the efficient use of energy and operational resources.

The National Chamber of Aquaculture points out that an inventory of shrimp farms covers around 250,000 hectares located on the Ecuadorian coast and at least half of the farms do not have highly efficient pumping systems, which means that the level of competitiveness of the sector at the national level is not what was expected, especially from small and medium producers.

This energy planning project plans to connect the shrimp farms to the public electricity grid (the connection cost will be provided by the government and not by the shrimp farms), which will allow the use of state-of-the-art electric pumps and technology that will support a leap in productivity of the shrimp sector and in its operational efficiency.

METHODOLOGY

When quantifying the energy consumed in pumping water, which in this case is that produced by diesel combustion, we do so indirectly use the heating value of diesel in terms of kwh/Gal.

In this context, the key indicator to seek efficiency in a pumping system is the cost in USD/m³ of pumped water, since the concept of optimizing energy consumption in a pumping station means obtaining the required amount of water at the lowest possible cost.

By performing a sensitivity analysis, based on pump efficiency, with three types of pumps, each with a different level of technology and therefore efficiency, it can be stated that as pump efficiency increases, the required engine power decreases; Therefore, the power consumption of the motor is reduced.

Most medium and small-sized shrimp farms in Ecuador, which represent almost 75 percent of the country's total farms, use pumping systems with an energy efficiency of around 50 percent.

By using electric motors in the pumping system, the annual savings in USD that the shrimp industry would have by replacing diesel engines would be greater specially for larger motor powers

With the data obtained from the sensitivity analysis of the pumps and the inventory of the shrimp farms, a coefficient was established for the commodity of electrical energy and using the SUT model, the activities and commodities involved in the Results of the Annual National Accounts of the Central Bank of Ecuador, from the year 2020 (Supply – Use table) were established.

As part of the MARIO modeling process, a valuation was carried out based on Production and a baseline GDP was established and a shock was caused, obtaining a GDP shock, which when the respective balance was carried out produced a variation in the GDP and of the production.

GDP Baseline		GDP Shock	
Variable	Variable Value	Variable	Variable Value
Diesel fuel (KUSD)	85589	Diesel fuel (KUSD)	0
Electricity power KUSD	0	Electricity power Coefficient	0,03738

Table 1: GDP Baseline & GDP Shock

which leads to thinking that changes in technology or in the energy source, may have unanticipated side effects that negatively affect production in other sectors of the economy, which could contribute to an overall decline in production at the national level.

If switching to electricity carries higher costs compared to diesel, especially if diesel is subsidized, this could increase production costs for shrimp farms and ultimately lead to a decline in production.

If the electrical infrastructure is not adequately developed or unreliable, the switch to electricity could result in frequent interruptions in the power supply, which would negatively affect production in shrimp farms and other economic sectors.

If the increase in GDP comes primarily from sectors of the economy that are less productive in terms of generating added value per unit of labor or capital, this could result in an increase in GDP without a corresponding increase in productivity.

Finally, if the economy experiences a financial crisis, natural disasters, or sudden changes in commodity prices, an increase in GDP may not necessarily reflect an increase in productivity due to disruptions to normal economic activity.

CONCLUSION

The development of this prefeasibility project began in 2015 and is currently in the feasibility stage. Given the current economic circumstances of the country, it is concluded that an update of the project that incorporates the new specific conditions to be evaluated would be advisable.

It can be concluded that when modeling a production activity associated with commodities, any significant change in the technology and/or energy source used in a specific sector would have to be carefully evaluated based on the specific conditions of the country and its economy.

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